

HOW DO SIGNAGE DESIGN INFLUENCE USER'S BEHAVIOR :

A CASE STUDY OF REDESIGN THE WAY-FINDING AND SIGNAGE SYSTEM FOR SHANGHAI SOUTH RAILWAY STATION

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ABSTRACT

This project looks at how passengers find their way in the complicated transportation building, and considers how people can be encouraged to take public transport through clear and conscious signage guiding. Through the research and design process, a new signage system combined with the existing system in Shanghai south railway station was put into use in 2010. The result appears positive that the redesign improved the flow circulation status and made a beneficial impact on the transportation system.

The conclusion is that the properly and purposed research and design of way-finding system can lead to a more sustainable behavior and deliver significant environmental and economic benefits not only for transport building but for all the public spaces.

Keywords: Way-finding research, Signage Design, Behavior, transportation building

BACKGROUND

Shanghai South Railway Station occupied sixty hectares of land and serves most trains to the Southern provinces of China. After extensive renovation that was finished in 2006, the station features a modern circular design, the first of its kind in the world. The station itself is elevated 47 meters above ground and the ground area is 58,145 square meters, 122,916 square meters underground. The station area is a huge transport hub Integrated with railway station, coach station (40,000 square meters), 3 subway lines (one line still in plan), 14 bus starting

stations, taxi and private car. Above that, a shopping center of 60,000 square meters underground make this site a commercial center of the surrounding area. (YU Wei, GU Ying-qi, 2010)

After the station put into use in 2007, daily average passenger flow reached around 300,000 people. At the same time, a lot of complaints against the legibility and the way-finding of the space appeared. The volunteers who help people to find their way were asked around 100-200 times/day/person, besides them the security and cleaners are also carrying the duty of guiding passengers (ZHANG Hai-ye and YAN Ke-fei, 2007). Passengers were frustrated by the complicated space and unclear signage system, this not only affected the efficiency of traffic circulation also had a negative impact on passengers' emotions.

For the 2010 Shanghai World Expo, the south railway station will be the most important transport center and the estimated passenger flow will reach 400,000-500,000 persons/day (In fact the highest passenger flow even reach to 600,000 persons/day). Methods of this traffic flow evaluation for such a large numbers in the shortest time will give huge challenge to the area traffic and the way-finding system.

Figure 1. Shanghai south railway station.

In this context, the Construction and Transportation Committee of Xujiahui district and the South Railway Station Management Committee invited our team to do the research and redesign project for Shanghai south railway station area way-finding system. The Research and design took place from September 2008 and finished implementation in April 2010.

RESEARCH AND CONSULTATIONS

We have studied the site and the existing sign system, reviewed similar design and research cases to identify the major issues. In the course of our research we have met with officers from the management committee of the station and interviewed many passengers to build up a balanced overview. The results of the main problems are summarized as below:

The site

- The round shape of the building makes people lose the sense of direction. (Figure 2: F)
- The exits of the station are underground, which increase the difficulty to navigating. (Figure 2: A)
- Many passages and gateways, easy to be confused.
- Huge instantaneous flow reduces the readability of common signs.
- The passages and gateways are different from daytime and nighttime.
- The bus stations are located on north and South Square, the connection of them is underground and not easy to find.
- There are totally 16 entrances and exits with different destinations.

Figure 2. Photos of the existing signage system for Shanghai south railway station

The existing signage system

- The hierarchy of way-finding information is not clear. (Figure 2:A,D)

- Lack of ground public traffic information at the exits of underground spaces. (Figure 2: C)
- Most of the signage using the standard size of fonts and icons, the readable distance in the site status is too short. (Figure 2: B)
- The location of signs needs to be developed.
- The readability of the sign maps need to be improved.

OBJECTIVES

As Fewings stated the principles of wayfinding are simple; the practicalities are very complex (Fewings, R. 2001). Our aim is to identify a practical solution to better way-finding and outline the principles of a train station signage system that helps rapid circulation. Through this solution not only make the site easier to understand for users but also encourage passengers to take public transport.

To redesign a signage system, we must be mindful of what matters to the different kinds of users in Shanghai south railway station, and take into account the needs of the railway passengers, coach passengers, subway transfer passengers or shoppers. All of these have legitimate concerns that must be reconciled to make a system work.

Figure 3. Illustration of passengers' behavior analysis

Before we redesign the system we must take full account of what is there at the moment to decide what needs to stay, go, or be improved. The defining characteristic of the present situation, viewed as a whole, is that it is provider-led and not customer-led

(YIN Zheng-sheng, 2008). As Patricia Brown noted we know from the worlds of commerce and industry that this is not the best way of meeting the needs of the very providers who, by default, have had to institute these systems. In other words, if we think about the needs of passengers who are willing to take public transport we will be more effective in encouraging them to do that than if we focus primarily on our own need to promote a particular route or destination. (Patricia Brown, 2006).

Through our interview, many passengers avoid taking public transport if it requires them to navigate through an unfamiliar territory. The sense of the unknown – how long will it take, where a street leads to – creates 'risk', especially of getting lost or increase journey times. In contrast, taking taxi will be an easier choice even they may have to pay more, wait in line or encounter traffic jams. This situation enlarged the needs for taxi and self-driving or parking, burdened to the Shanghai south railway station's taxi and public parking supply. (Figure 3)

It is for this reason that the management committee of the station cooperated with us to redesign the signage system, aimed to not only a more integrated way-finding system but also guide a more sustainable and economical behavior.

METHODOLOGY

ACUPUNCTURE

Shanghai south railway station is a complex site combined with indoor, outdoor and underground

spaces, the signage system have to service a wide variety of needs. Therefore all the things that are successfully achieved by the present signage systems would need to be carefully considered in any new system. While to solve the problem of the exiting system we try to adopted a traditional Chinese medicine method – acupuncture.

Figure 4. Illustration of acupuncture

Acupuncture is a type of alternative medicine that treats patients by insertion and manipulation of solid, generally thin needles in the body. This redesign adopts the acupuncture approach. Single initiatives unified in a general framework can have a systemic effect. In the same way as acupuncture adequately stimulates key acupoints to affect the whole meridian system, find and redesign the key point in the old system will form a strong cooperative network to generate effects in the whole system of the entire site. (LOU Yong-qi,2010)

Figure 5. The "acupuncture" redesign process and outcome

The acupoints in Shanghai south railway station could be summarized in several main flow block point, in which passengers have doubts on decision making. In such key decision points, we try to set large size directional signs with straight and clear information to help users read, accept, process information and make decision in the shortest time. In this case, the acupuncture needles, that is, over scale signs with eye-catching colors (the chose colors fit the subway line colors) and simple graphics (Figure 5).Through passenger flow line analysis we find out that the north and south exits of the station were always the most block point and those could be described as the "acupuncture points". By adding such signs on the acupoints the hierarchy of the original sign system was greatly reformed and the whole way-finding system therefore was improved.

CUSTOMER-LED METHOD : LEAD TO A BETTER BEHAVIOR

Putting the needs of users first, requires that we appreciate the many different kinds of (potential) users: railway passengers, coach passengers, subway transfer passengers and shoppers. Their needs are not met well at present. Even if one signage system is excellent in meeting its own brief, it will have to work harder to guide behavior than a common way-finding system (Applied Information Group, 2007).

If we consider the needs of users in general, we may extrapolate some principles on which everyone can agree as the starting point for a common agenda. All kinds of walkers want to:

- Know where to look for way-finding information when they need it.
- Understand the way in which the information is communicated.
- Obtain the information they want quickly, intuitively and without fuss.

It is in everyone’s interest to make the user’s experience a positive one.

As designers, we may, in addition, want to service specific requirements, such as:

- Promote / drive people to a particular destination (e.g. bus station or subway station)
- Promote the character / identity of the space
- Reduce vision clutter

- Reinforce awareness of the space
- Encouraging the better option through signage guide

Through our research, people are willing to take the public transport if they feel the transfer trip is manageable and reliable. This means we can achieve a considerable benefit from providing information about the alternative public transport option instead of taking taxi at the point at which users are making decisions.

Showing large-size signs at the exit of railway station that the metro line direction is next to it, the close bus station is just on the upper floor, and the taxi waiting point is another direction, is likely to have a significant impact on the route choices of users– encouraging people to take public transport instead of taxi or private car. This approach can be maximized and supported with a hierarchy of information support, including direction signs, site maps and route signs.

DATA AND FINDINGS

By April 2010, totally 241 sign panels were redesigned or newly added into the signage system. During 2010 Shanghai World Expo, the highest passenger flow reaches to 600,000 persons per day and was evacuated successfully.

STATISTICAL DATA

We choose the statistical data in the condition of same flow/day in 2007 and 2011, and compared the approximate data of passengers taking subway, taxi and self driving.

	2007	2011
Subway passengers (persons/day)	90,000	100,000-110,000
Taxi (taxis/day)	500-600	600
Self-driving parking (cars/day)	100-150	100

Table 1. statistical data comparison between 2007 and 2011.(data sources: the management committee of Shanghai South Railway station), (the subway data is also influenced by the improvement of the network coverage)

USER RESEARCH DATA

In collaboration with the Shanghai south railway station management committee, we conducted field research questioning passengers as they left the station in March 2011. The findings are summarized below.

Respondent profile:

- 192 people were surveyed.
- 67% were railway passengers, 27% were coach passengers, 5% were subway transfer, the remainder were shoppers.

Key findings:

- 73% of railway and coach passengers had looked at signs or maps inside the station before exiting.
- 98% were comfortable with signs in the station.
- 86% of railway and coach passengers intended to take subway or bus to their destinations.
- 87% could correctly identify the direction to the subway or bus station.
- 93% think the direction sign of subway and bus station is clear and easy to find
- 65% of visitors think the map on the sign is easy to understand and 74% said they will read the map for navigating.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The case study, research and considerations set out in this report have led us to conclude that the properly and purposed research and design of way-finding system can lead to a more sustainable behavior and deliver significant environmental and economic benefits not only for transport building but for all the public spaces.

To guide users' behavior requires an integrated interdisciplinary cooperation and research, such as this redesign team has an integrated team from the

architectural design, transportation engineering, industrial design, visual communication design, environmental design and other professional designers.

As many fast developing cities, Shanghai is still continuing to build and improve the urban infrastructure and public facilities. In 2011, another new transport hub put into use, and during 2011-2020 eight new subway lines will be built. How to circulate instantaneous huge number of passengers, how to guide a more sustainable and economical behavior, these will be worth to research and will make the case study worthy of popularization. The research and redesign project got many good feedbacks both from the users and the managers, and was awarded as demonstration project by the Shanghai Construction and Transportation Committee in 2011.

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